

*"Gh. Știrbei" Institute for
Social Sciences and the
Humanities.*

**DIMITRIE CANTEMIR
UNIVERSITY**
Tirgu Mures

13TH EDITION

*THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE*

GLOBALIZATION, INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE AND NATIONAL IDENTITY

16-17 MAY 2026

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CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

SATURDAY – 16 MAY 2026

10⁰⁰ - 11⁰⁰ - Welcome and Opening

11⁰⁰ - 13⁰⁰ – Paper Presentations on Sections:

- **Literature**
- **Language and Discourse**
- **Communication and Public Relations**
- **Journalism**
- **History and Cultural Mentalities**
- **Psychology and Educational Science**
- **Political Sciences, International Relations**
- **Sociology**
- **Social Sciences**

15⁰⁰ - 18⁰⁰ - Paper Presentations on Sections

SUNDAY – 17 MAY 2026

11⁰⁰ - 15⁰⁰ – Paper Presentations on Sections

**The conference is organised in partnership by:
"Alpha" Institute for Multicultural Studies
"Gh. Șincai" Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities
"Dimitrie Cantemir" University of Tîrgu-Mureș**

A WORD
FROM THE PRESIDENT OF THE CONFERENCE

DEAR GUESTS,

Having established a certain tradition in the recent years, the International Conference *GLOBALIZATION, INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE AND NATIONAL IDENTITY* (now at its 13th edition) intends to unite emerging scholars, as well as prestigious researchers from different fields of radical relevance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. Literature, the cultural discourses as well as the arts gain new connections and dimensions through fundamental changes and structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research becomes extremely important. It is a fact that in our postmodern times, we live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life, but to the risks and dangers of which we are at the same time exposed. *Non scholae sed vitae discimus* (*We do not learn for the school, but for life*) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. It is essential that the path between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this interesting and captivating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting works and papers, together with ideas generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

I wish to express my hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

Prof. IULIAN BOLDEA, PhD
President of the *GIDNI 13* Conference

SATURDAY – 16 MAY 2026

LITERATURE

Moderators: Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Prof. Mina Maria Rusu, PhD, „Apollonia” University of Iași; Assoc. Prof. Mariana Baloșescu, PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava

1. Iulian Boldea, Prof. PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *MATEI VIȘNIEC. CONFLUENCES BETWEEN POETRY AND THEATER*
2. Mina-Maria Rusu, Prof., PhD, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica” Bucharest, Pitești University Center, „Apollonia” University of Iași, *ON THE VOCATION OF RE-CREATING THE FIRST WORLD*
3. Călina Nicoleta Presură, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *TRANSLATION AND THE CULTURAL FUNCTION OF CARMEN SYLVA’S (ELISABETH OF ROMANIA) WORKS WITHIN THE ITALIAN CULTURAL SPHERE*
4. Mariana Baloșescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *ETHICAL IMAGINATION IN FLAUBERT AND HOULLEBECQ*
5. Lioara Elena Coturbaș, Senior Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, *STYLISTIC DIMENSIONS IN MIRCEA ELIADE’S PROSE*
6. Iudit Călinescu, Senior Lecturer, PhD, University of Szeged, Institute of the Romanian Language, Bucharest, *PHENOMENOLOGICAL MYTHS OF ORIGIN: COSMOGONY AND ANTHROPOGONY IN COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVE*

7. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest, *ATTACHMENT TO BRITISH IDENTITY IN A SELECTION OF GRAHAM SWIFT'S WORKS*
8. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest, *FAIRY-TALES AND MAGIC AS A FRAMEWORK FOR THE NOVELS MOTHERING SUNDAY AND HERE WE ARE BY GRAHAM SWIFT*
9. Maria Lațchici, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *EXPRESSIONIST ELEMENTS IN MIROSLAV KRLEŽA'S DRAMATURGY*
10. Simona Șuta, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, *THE SCIENCE OF THE MIND: BETWEEN AUTOMATISM, DREAMS, AND THE UNCONSCIOUS AMONG THE FRENCH SURREALISTS*
11. Ioana Raicu, Lecturer, PhD, "Valahia" University of Târgoviște, *POSTMODERNISM AT ITS BEST IN JOHN FOWLES'S THE EBONY TOWER*
12. Cosmina Cristescu, Lecturer, PhD, "Transilvania" University of Brașov, *ROMANIAN TEXTBOOKS, POETRY, COMMUNISM, PROPAGANDA, CURRICULA*
13. Lavinia Similaru, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *RIVALRY AMONG WOMEN ACCORDING TO BENITO PÉREZ GALDÓS*
14. Mihaela-Anca Ogășanu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, *WITIN IHIMAERA REVISITED*
15. Iulian Băicuș, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *THE MIHAIL SEBASTIAN CASE*
16. Iulian Băicuș, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *PARALLEL LIVES, BIOGRAPHIES OF MARCEL PROUST*
17. Cristina Lizeta Furtună, Lecturer, PhD, „Valahia” University of Târgoviște, *SYMBOLIC AND IDENTITY DIMENSIONS OF FEMININITY IN THE INTERWAR NOVEL*

18. Emanuel-Daniel Sărmășan, Assist. Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *CLEOPATRA VII: AT THE INTERSECTION OF DIPLOMACY AND EROTIC LITERATURE*
19. Emanuel-Daniel Sărmășan, Assist. Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *HERTA MÜLLER. AT THE INTERSECTION OF TRAUMA AND THE AESTHETICS OF THE UGLY: THE SHADOWS OF THE PAST IN FEMINIST LITERATURE*
20. Antonia Pop, Assist. Prof., PhD, Partium Christian University, *CONFRONTING PERSONAL TRUTHS IN PETER SHAFFER'S DRAMA*
21. Anca Rusu, Assist., PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *BETWEEN OPPOSITION AND ATTRACTION: STEINHARDT'S READING OF BOGZA*
22. Daria Pârvu, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *FLESH AND FAITH: ROBERT BROWNING'S "FRA LIPPO LIPPI" AND THE CONFLICT BETWEEN REALISM AND RELIGIOUS IDEALISM IN ART*
23. Dumitrița Maximciuc, Assist. Prof., PhD, Academy of Music, Theatre and Fine Arts, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *MEMORY, IDENTITY, AND SURVIVAL IN THE MONODRAMA SFATURILE MELANIEI BY IRINA NECHIT: A DRAMATURGICAL MODEL OF NARRATIVE FRAGMENTATION*
24. Roxana-Silvia Moraru, Assist. Prof., PhD, “Vasile Goldiș” Western University of Arad, *REDEFINING THE INNER SELF OF A POSTMODERN MUSICIAN*
25. Mariana Cocieru, Scientific Researcher, PhD, Moldova State University, *DEMONS OF THE THRESHOLD AND SPIRITS OF THE WILDERNESS: MAPPING MYTHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS IN MAGICAL TEXTS*

26. Carmen Mihaela Potlog, PhD, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, *OUTSIDE THE TEXT*
27. Dimitrie Andrei Borcan, PhD, "Ovidius" University of Constanța, *AMBIGUITY AND MIRRORING IN AN ECOCRITICAL ANALYSIS OF T. S. ELIOT'S "THE WASTE LAND"*
28. Dimitrie Andrei Borcan, PhD, "Ovidius" University of Constanța, *AN ECOCRITICAL APPROACH TO WALT WHITMAN'S "SONG OF MYSELF"*
29. Diana Grumeza, PhD, "Ștefan cel Mare" University of Suceava, *THE FEMALE INTIMATE DIARY: PARADIGMS AND REPRESENTATIONS*
30. Alina Dorle, PhD, "Vasile Lucaciu, National College, Baia Mare, *ION BARBU WITHIN THE POETIC LABYRINTH OF THE WORD*
31. Laurențiu Boșog, PhD, University of Craiova, *THE VICTORIAN WOMAN TRAVELLER: A POLITICAL ENTITY*
32. Maria Beatrice Lucaciu, PhD, University of Oradea, *GALA GALACTION – AN AUTHOR OF FANTASTIC PROSE*
33. Maria-Nicoleta Pop, PhD, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *TO BE AND NOT TO BELONG: IDENTITY DILEMMAS IN THE WRITINGS OF MIHAIL SEBASTIAN FROM AN INTERCULTURAL PERSPECTIVE*
34. Horia Mihai Răuț Băbuță, PhD, "Babeș-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca, West University of Timișoara, *AKTIONSGRUPPE BANAT AND THE REDEFINITION OF ROMANIAN-GERMAN LITERARY IDENTITY BETWEEN MINORITY, DISSENT AND INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE*
35. Maria-Loredana Simionovici, PhD, "Ștefan cel Mare" University of Suceava, *SOLIPSISM AND THE INTELLECTUAL OUTSIDER: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FAUST AND HARRY HALLER*

36. Ioana-Mihaela Vultur, PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureş, *ANA BLANDIANA, A MODEL OF ETHICAL ILINX*
37. Teodora Voinescu, PhD, The National College of Computer Sciences “Grigore Moisil”, Braşov, *THE MAN BETWEEN TIMES: THE CONSTRUCTION OF IDENTITY AND THE ROLE OF MEMORY IN DALIA SOFER'S THE MAN OF MY TIME*
38. Gabriela Buta, PhD, “St. Gheorghe” Middle School, Sângeorgiu de Mureş, *MORAL VALUES IN LITERARY AND RELIGIOUS TEXTS*
39. Anca-Mihaela Dosan, PhD, "Carmen Sylva" National College of Computer Science, Petroşani, Hunedoara County, *THE CHILD-HERO VERSUS THE HERO-CHILD: TOWARD A COMPOSITE FIGURE*
40. Stela Pleşa, PhD, Racoviţa Middle School, Sibiu County, *AN ONTO-AESTHETIC APPROACH TO LESLEY SAUNDERS' POETRY*
41. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE SYMPHONY OF THE SOUL: FRAGILITY, MEMORY, AND DIVINE MERCY IN PSALM 103*
42. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE MARK OF THE UNCONVENTIONAL AND THE SEARCH FOR SPIRITUAL IDENTITY IN 20TH-CENTURY DRAMA: THE CASE OF EUGEN IONESCU VS. SAMUEL BECKETT*
43. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *WILLIAM BLAKE AND THE RECEPTION OF HIS WORKS IN POST-DECEMBER ROMANIA: A RENAISSANCE OF CULTURAL AWARENESS AMONG IMAGE, TEXT, AND IMAGINATION*
44. Ileana Dora Voiculescu (Mirea), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *G. CĂLINESCU'S LINGUISTIC CULTURE*

45. Ileana Dora Voiculean (Mirea), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE NEOLOGICAL LEXICON IN THE ROMANIAN LITERARY LANGUAGE (1881-1960)*
46. Dana Gianina Popescu, PhD Student, "Valahia" University of Târgoviște, *LITERARY FOUNDATIONS IN EARLY EDUCATION: EXPLORING CHILDREN'S LITERATURE IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS*
47. Alexandra Ruscanu, PhD Student, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, *THEMATOLOGICAL MUTATIONS OF THE 20TH-CENTURY NOVEL. THE DYSTOPIAN NOVEL*
48. Andreia-Elena Mateoiu (Baltres), PhD Student, "1 Decembrie 1918" University of Alba Iulia, *BETWEEN HISTORY AND FICTION: MAGICAL REALISM AS A FORM OF INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE IN DIE BLECHTROMMEL*
49. Daniela Eugenia Stoian (Dinu), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *BETWEEN FRAGMENT AND VIGILANCE OF CONSCIOUSNESS: EMIL CIORAN'S NOTEBOOKS AND PAUL VALÉRY'S CAHIERS*
50. Andreea-Maria Popescu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Centre, *THE THEME OF LOVE REFLECTED IN THE EXISTENTIAL TOPOI OF BOGDAN SUCEAVĂ'S POETRY*
51. Rebeca-Daniela Stănescu, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Centre, *URMUZ AND POSTMODERNISM OR THE POST-TRUTH ERA*
52. Viorica Olaru, PhD Student, Moldova State University, *ALEXANDER GROMOV – BEYOND REALITY'S LIMITS*
53. Adriana-Maria Călugăr (Cutean), PhD Student, "1 December 1918" University of Alba Iulia, *THE ARCHITECTURE OF FEAR IN STALINIST ROMANIA – THE ADOPTION OF THE SOVIET "MODEL"*

54. Ioana-Cristina Pătrună, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *BETWEEN SATIRE AND SOCIAL CRITIQUE: REPRESENTING POST-COMMUNIST REALITY IN DINU SĂRARU'S CIOCOI TRILOGY*
55. Ana-Maria Torkos, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *TOWARDS AN ETHICS OF THOUGHT: DISCIPLINE, ATTENTION, AND SELF-TRANSFORMATION IN PAUL VALÉRY'S NOTEBOOKS*
56. Manuela Varga, Student PhD, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *"STARDUST"—A SPACE BETWEEN LITERATURE AND CINEMA*
57. Ioan Alexandru Murar, PhD Student, University of Pitești, *THE EXISTENTIAL DOUBLE — TOWARDS AN INQUIRY INTO HUMAN IDENTITY AS THE GROUND OF A TRAUMARIST EXPERIENCE IN I IS ANOTHER (SEPTOLOGY III-V) BY JON FOSSE*
58. Bogdan Ioan Macarie, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *ROMANIAN PROTOCRONISM: FROM COMPARATIVE HYPOTHESIS TO NATIONALIST IDEOLOGICAL DISCOURSE*
59. Cristia Cucuș, PhD Candidate, "Alecă Russo" Bălți State Univeristy, Republic of Moldova, Oxana Chira, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Alecă Russo" Bălți State Univeristy, Republic of Moldova, *CULINARY LEXICON AS AN EXPRESSION OF IDENTITY AND MEMORY IN THE NOVEL GLASS GARDEN BY TATIANA ȚÎBULEAC*
60. Diana-Ioana Feurdean, PhD Candidate, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *MYTHICAL HYPOSTASES OF THE ROMANIAN VILLAGE IN THE LYRIC POETRY OF LUCIAN BLAGA*
61. Alina Neculachi, PhD Candidate, University of Bucharest, *FOUR NOVELISTS OF THE 1960S GENERATION:*

CONSTANTIN ȚOIU, D.R. POPESCU, NICOLAE BREBAN,
AUGUSTIN BUZURA

62. Teodora Fărăgău, Master's Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, Ionela Cecilia Șulea, Teacher in state gymnasium education and Educational adviser at University „Dimitrie Cantemir” from Târgu Mureș, Maria Zamfira Căbuz, Teacher in state high school education „Transilvania” College of Economy from Târgu Mureș, *HORTENSIA PAPADAT-BENGESCU. AN EXCURSION INTO THE HALLIPS' UNIVERSE, FROM THE UNTANGLED VIRGINS TO BACH'S CONCERTO*
63. Anghel Costa, MA Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *SUBVERSIONS OF THE BUCOLIC IN IOAN SLAVICI'S NOVELLAS*
64. Iulia Ileana Baiduca, Master's Student, Univeristy of Oradea, Mihaela Ogășanu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, „*THE DIRECTOR'S CUT OF MEMORY: FRAMING, EDITING, AND THE CINEMATIC REALITY IN MIDNIGHT'S CHILDREN*”
65. Maria Lazăr, PhD Student, “1 December 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *(ST)AGES OF BLINDNESS. BETWEEN METAPHOR AND DISABILITY IN “DUMINECA ORBULUI” AND “ZAHEI ORBUL”*

SATURDAY – 16 MAY 2026

LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE

Moderators: Prof. Floriana Popescu, PhD, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați; Lecturer Denisa Elena Petrehuș, PhD, "Babeș-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca; Lecturer Liliana Florina Andronache, PhD, „Carol Davila” University of Medicine and Pharmacy Bucharest

1. Floriana Popescu, Prof., PhD, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați, *TERMINOLOGICAL ONOMASTIC TRINOMIALS BETWEEN FIXEDNESS AND LOOSENESS*
2. Maria-Elena Milcu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Lucian Blaga" University of Sibiu, Elena Raluca Gheorghe, PhD Student, "Lucian Blaga" University of Sibiu, *ECOLINGUISTICS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS, HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT AND CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH PERSPECTIVES*
3. Camelia Alibec, Senior Lecturer, PhD, Romanian Naval Academy "Mircea cel Batran", Constanța, *MARITIME SLANG AND JARGON*
4. Dana Carmen Zechia, Lecturer, PhD, Romanian Naval Academy "Mircea cel Batran", Constanța, *CULTURE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING*
5. Florina-Maria Băcilă, Lecturer, PhD, "West University of Timișoara, *"THE INSUFFICIENCY OF LANGUAGE" AND THE COMPLEXITY OF THE RELATIONSHIP WITH DIVINITY IN TRAIAN DORZ'S POETRY*
6. Liliana Florina Andronache, Lecturer, PhD, The University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Carol Davila" Bucharest, *THE*

*GLOBALIZING EFFECT OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE ON
TEENAGE DISCOURSE*

7. Denisa Elena Petrehuş, Lecturer, PhD, “Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *LINGUISTIC TRAPS IN TRANSLATIONS*
8. Iustina Nica, 2nd Degree Scientific Researcher, PhD, “C.S. Nicolăescu-Plopşor” Scientific Research Institute, Romanian Academy, Craiova, *THE ETHNONYM ARBĂNAŞ IN THE ROMANIAN LANGUAGE: LEXICOGRAPHICAL, HISTORICAL, AND ONOMASTIC ATTESTATIONS*
9. Anca Ionescu, Independent Researcher, *INTERCULTURAL AND TERMINOLOGICAL CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ROMANIAN FOR NAVAL ARCHITECTURE TO UKRAINIAN REFUGEE STUDENTS*
10. Ileana Dora Voiculean (Mirea), PhD, Univeristy of Craiova, *THE LINGUISTIC CULTURE OF G. CĂLINESCU*
11. Ileana Dora Voiculean (Mirea), PhD, Univeristy of Craiova, *NEOLOGICAL VOCABULARY IN LITERARY ROMANIAN (1881–1960)*
12. Adela Sava (Codreş), PhD, Moldova State University, *TOPOI, COMMONPLACES, STEREOTYPES, AND CLICHÉS IN THE WORKS OF IRÈNE NÉMIROVSKY*
13. Claudia-Sorina Barbu (Popa), PhD, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, University Center of Piteşti, *CURRENT CHALLENGES IN THE FIELD OF TEACHING AND LEARNING MODERN LANGUAGES*
14. Ioana-Georgiana Bahrin, PhD, “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iaşi, *PRAGMATIC DIMENSIONS OF THE CONGRATULATORY DISCOURSE IN SPANISH ROYAL RETHORIC*

15. Loredana Georgiana Popescu (Tomescu), PhD, „University of Craiova, *THE HUMOROUS EFFECT OF HOMONYMY IN THE ONLINE ENVIRONMENT*
16. Sebastian Dragoş Mihai, PhD Student, University of Piteşti, *LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF CONTEMPORARY ELECTORAL DISCOURSE*
17. Eugenia Ioana Ciobanu (Vlad), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *TERMINOGRAPHIC DEFINITIONS AND LEXICOGRAPHIC DEFINITIONS IN THE FIELD OF METALLURGY. TERMS FROM ASRO STANDARDS AND FROM DEX*
18. Ancuţa Lungu (Dumitru), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND METHODOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES*
19. Gabriela Bădescu (Cojocar), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, University Center of Piteşti, *THE ARCHAEOLOGY OF WORDS AND THE POLYPHONY OF MEMORY IN GABRIELA ADAMEŞTEANU'S PROSE – ARCHAISMS, REGIONALISMS, COLLOQUIALISMS, NEOLOGISMS, AND THE ORIGINALITY OF THE WORK*
20. Mirela-Simona Gurău (Rusu), PhD Student, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galaţi, *ACRONYMS IN ROMANIAN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY: AN ACADEMIC OVERVIEW*
21. Marta-Cristina Negraia Burghiu, PhD Student, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galaţi, *THE DISCURSIVE FRAMING OF MUSLIM WOMEN IN THE FRENCH PRESS THROUGH DISCURSIVE MEMORY*
22. Denis-Alin-Florin Diaconu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *ELEMENTS OF THE AESTHETICS OF UGLINESS IN THE POETRY OF ANTON PANN: WORD FORMATION*

23. Maria-Magdalena Diaconu (Marian), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *COMMERCIAL PRODUCT NAMES: DAIRY*
24. Isabelle Nicole Voicu, PhD Student, "Lucian Blaga" University of Sibiu, *CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS AS A PRACTICAL TOOL FOR NAVIGATING AI-GENERATED AND MEDIA DISCOURSE IN THE 21ST CENTURY*
25. Maria Cristina Bogdan, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *MONOSEMANTICISM IN MINERALOGICAL TERMINOLOGY: LEXICOLOGICAL AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS*
26. Ana-Larisa Pelin Doca-Trincu, PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *DÉTOURNEMENT AS A DISCURSIVE PRACTICE IN PRESS HEADLINES: AN INTERPRETIVE APPROACH*
27. Maria-Loredana Pleșca, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *CORRECTIONS IN CHILDREN'S SPEECH: A PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS*
28. Elena-Daniela Strigoiu (Marinescu), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *TYPES OF AUGMENTATION*
29. Ica-Emilia Udriște, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology, Politehnica Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *THE USE OF NEOLOGISMS IN GALA GALACTION'S PROSE*
30. Elena-Georgiana Udrescu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *FINANCIAL LEXICON. MONOSEMY AND POLYSEMY*
31. Paula Munteanu, PhD Candidate, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *DIACHRONIC, DIATOPIC AND DIAPHASIC DYNAMISM OF THE “VERICE” AND “VERICINE” FORMS*

SATURDAY – 16 MAY 2026

***COMMUNICATION, JOURNALISM, EDUCATION
SCIENCES, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIOLOGY***

Moderators: Prof. Teodor Pătrăuță, PhD, "Vasile Goldiș" Western University of Arad; Assoc. Prof. Maria Pleșca, PhD, "Ion Creangă" State Pedagogical University, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova; Assoc. Prof. Laura Ioana Leon, PhD, „Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iași

1. Teodor Pătrăuță, Prof., PhD, “Vasile Goldiș” Western University of Arad, *THE EXPANSION OF INTERCULTURALISM AND MULTICULTURALISM: A PARADIGM OF MODERN EDUCATION*
2. Sorina-Mihaela Bălan, Assoc. Prof., PhD, “Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureș, Crisanta-Alina Mazilescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, West University of Timișoara, *ETHICAL USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND COGNITIVE AUTONOMY IN CONTEMPORARY LEARNING*
3. Laura Ioana Leon, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iași, *PICTURE BOOKS AS NARRATIVE MODELS: INSIGHTS FROM KEIRA KNIGHTKEY’S I LOVE YOU JUST THE SAME (2025)*
4. Maria Pleșca, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Ion Creangă" State Pedagogical University, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *PERCEIVED LONELINESS AND PSYCHOSOCIAL ADAPTATION AMONG STUDENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF CONTEMPORARY ACADEMIC CHALLENGES*
5. Veronica Păstae, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Carol I National Defense University, Bucharest, Luiza Maria Costea, Prof., PhD, Carol

- I National Defense University, Bucharest, *POWER IN INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION*
6. Corneliu Sigmirean, Lecturer, PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *ARCHIVING IN THE CLOUD ERA: NEW PARADIGMS IN DOCUMENT PRESERVATION*
 7. Victoria Maximciu, Lecture, PhD, „Ion Creangă” Pedagogical State University, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL SKILLS AMONG YOUNG SPECIALISTS IN NEUROPSYCHOLOGY*
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SATURDAY – 16 MAY 2026

***HISTORY, POLITICAL SCIENCES, INTERNATIONAL
RELATIONS***

Moderators: Prof. Cornel Sigmirean, PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureş; Prof. Ioana Iulia Olaru, PhD, „George Enescu” National University of Arts, Iaşi; Assoc. Prof. Adrian-Claudiu Stoica, PhD, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest.

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SATURDAY – 16 MAY 2026

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Moderators: Prof. Lucreția Dogaru, PhD, UMFST “G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș; Prof. Elena Doval, PhD, “Spiru Haret” University of Bucharest; Prof. Anca-Ileana Dușcă, PhD, University of Craiova

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